

1 **Interferon pathway activation in human HSC.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total gene expression by microarray in the hematopoietic stem cell (HSC) and in human
8 embryonic stem cells (hES) to identify defining expression features of the human HSC. Interferon signaling
9 is thought to be intrinsically linked to the primitive state of the ES cell. We describe here activation of the
10 interferon pathway in HSC characterized by induction of the innate immune receptor *Sting1* and the
11 interferon-stimulated gene *Irf16*.

12 Citations

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